

Determination and Separation of Palladium(II) and Nickel(II) using Morpholine-4-Carbodithioate

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Manuscript received 9 August 1978, revised 28 February 1979,
accepted 6 June 1979

IN the present investigation, morpholine-4-carbodithioate has been employed for the gravimetric determination of Pd(II) and Ni(II) and their separation in binary mixture. The mixture of ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate (1 : 1 molar ratio) has been used as masking agent for Ni(II). The thermolysis curve indicates that the aforesaid metal chelates are stable up to 220° and 320° respectively.

In continuation of our earlier work¹⁻³ on Te(IV), Cu(II) and Bi(III) complexes of morpholine-4-carbodithioate, we report here the results of determination, separation, and thermogravimetric analysis of morpholine-4-carbodithioate complexes of palladium and nickel.

Method and Material

The potassium salt of the reagent was prepared by mixing potassium hydroxide, morpholine and carbon disulphide in ether at 0° in a ratio 1 : 1 : 1. The purity of the reagent was confirmed by elemental analysis and I.R. spectra. The solutions of palladium chloride and nickel ammonium sulphate were prepared in water by usual methods.

Gravimetric Determination of Palladium and Nickel :

Respective metal ion solution containing 6.0-50.0 mg of the metal was diluted to about 150 ml with distilled water and the pH was adjusted in between 5.0-6.0 by adding the acetate buffer (acetic acid + sod. acetate). 1%(w/v) solution of the reagent was added with constant stirring. A coloured precipitate, yellow(Pd) and yellowish green in case of nickel gradually separated out. It was digested on water bath at 60°-70° for about 30-40 minutes. The precipitate was filtered in sintered crucible(G-4), washed repeatedly with distilled water, dried at 110-120° and weighed as $M(C_4H_8ONS_2)_2$.

It has also been noted that Pd(II) and Ni(II) were quantitatively precipitated in pH range 2.0 to 11.0 and 3.0 to 10.0 respectively. The results of thirty estimations of Pd(II) and Ni(II) over a pH range 5.0-6.5 revealed that 3.0 to 6.0 mgs of Pd(II) and Ni(II) could be determined with an average error better than $\pm 0.40\%$. The conversion factor (metal/metal-complex) were 0.2469 and 0.1532 for

Pd(II) and Ni(II) respectively. The complexes are soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, DMF and chloroform.

Determination of Pd(II) in Presence of Foreign Ions :

A 10 ml (0.20 M) of metal ion solution was mixed with a known amount of foreign ion and diluted to 150 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0 by using acetate buffer. A mixture of an ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate (1 : 1 molar ratio) was added to mask the Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Sn(II), In(III), Ga(III) and Tl(I) metal ions. In case of oxovanadium(IV) and oxotitanium(IV), 1 gm of sodium fluoride was added and contents were heated up to 50° on a water bath. The 1%(w/v) reagent solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. The chelate was filtered, washed, dried and weighed as described earlier. The ions Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , $C_2O_4^{2-}$, BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} , citrate, Ba(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Al(III), Th(IV), Zr(IV), U(VI) and W(VI) do not interfere in the determination of Pd(II) and Ni(II).

Thermal Decomposition of the Complexes :

The thermolysis curve of Pd-complex shows a horizontal level up to 220°. Above 220° slow decomposition starts, which continues up to 370° when a sudden decomposition takes place which continues up to 480°, thereafter the Pd-complex is finally converted to the Pd-metal.

The Ni-complex is thermally stable up to 320° above this temperature, rapid decomposition starts which continues up to 400° and thereafter a straight line is obtained up to 600°. The weight of the inorganic residue remains constant and consists of the mixture of $NiSO_4$ and NiO.

Separation and Determination of Pd(II) and Ni(II) in their Binary Mixture :

When Pd(II) and Ni(II) ions were present together in the solution, palladium was precipitated by masking nickel(II) with a mixture of ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate. The metals could be determined with an average error better than $\pm 0.5\%$.

The mixture of known volume of two ions was taken in a 500 ml beaker. It was diluted to 150 ml with distilled water. Appropriate quantity of the mixture of (1 : 1 molar ratio) ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate was added to mask the nickel(II). The pH of the solution was maintained in between 7.5-8.5. The metal is determined according to the procedure described earlier.

The filtrate of the palladium estimation containing nickel was concentrated to about 20 ml and after cooling it, 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid

(A.R.) was added. The solution was evaporated to dryness, diluted with 10 ml distilled water and again evaporated to dryness. After diluting it with 150 ml distilled water, any adherent of nitric acid was just neutralised by 1:1 ammonia solution. The 1%(w/v) reagent solution was then added, the yellowish green precipitate was determined as described earlier. The results of estimation of Pd(II) and Ni(II) are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AND Ni(II) IN THEIR BINARY MIXTURE

Metal ion taken (mg)		Complex obtained (mg)		Metal ion found (mg)		% Error	
Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)
12.00	11.72	48.6	78.8	12.00	11.76	0.00	+0.34
12.00	23.44	48.8	153.6	12.04	23.53	+0.33	+0.36
24.00	11.72	97.4	76.4	24.04	11.70	+0.16	-0.17
24.00	23.44	97.2	153.4	23.79	23.50	-0.04	+0.25
30.00	15.62	121.6	101.8	30.02	15.59	+0.06	-0.19
30.00	31.24	121.4	203.4	29.97	31.16	-0.10	-0.25

Acknowledgement

We wish to record our sincere thanks to Dr. R. N. Gupta, Principal and Dr. B. C. Banerjee (Reader), Hindu College, Moradabad, for providing all necessary facilities.

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Thiophene-2-Aldoxime as a Gravimetric Reagent for Rhodium(III)*

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Manuscript received 20 May 1978, revised 28 February 1979, accepted 6 June 1979

It has been found during investigation of analytical applications of thiophene-2-aldoxime in this laboratory that this reagent reacts with Rh(III) in neutral and alkaline medium to form a yellow-coloured complex which is insoluble in water and ethanol. A rapid gravimetric method for determination of rhodium based on this reaction is described.

* The paper was presented at the Convention of Chemists, Jaipur, 25-29th Dec., 1977.

Experimental

An expanded scale pH meter supplied by the Electronics Corporation of India, Ltd., Hyderabad, was employed for pH measurements. Rh(III) solutions were prepared from $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Johnson Matthey, London) and standardised¹ by reduction to Rh. Thiophene-2-aldehyde was prepared by the method described by Weston and Michaels². It was converted into its oxime by the usual method. The oxime, m. p. 132-34°, was used for the analytical work in the form of a 1% ethanolic solution.

Analysis of the yellow precipitate formed by Rh(III) with thiophene-2-aldoxime (found: Rh, 21.0%; C, 37.52%; H, 2.67%; N, 8.05%; S, 20.20%; required for $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{ONS})_3$: Rh, 21.4%; C, 37.42%; H, 2.50%; N, 8.73%; S, 19.96%) suggests it to be a tris-complex. It is stable to heat up to 120°.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results indicate that the precipitation of Rh(III) is quantitative in the pH range 10.5-11.0. It was also found that a 50% excess of the reagent over the calculated amount is required. The excess reagent can be easily removed by washing with hot water or 5% ethanol. The washed precipitate was dried at 110° and weighed. Table 1 shows the results

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF RHODIUM AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Rh(III) taken (mg)	Rh(III) found (mg)	% Error
4.56	4.25	6.80
9.11	9.08	0.33
13.67	13.61	0.44
18.22	18.23	0.05
22.78	22.68	0.44
27.33	27.31	0.07
31.89	31.67	0.67

of estimation of rhodium with the reagent at different amounts of the metal. It may be seen that rhodium, in amounts 10-30 mg can be determined gravimetrically with thiophene-2-aldoxime with a maximum error of 0.44%. Reproducibility studies carried out on five samples each containing 18.22 mg of Rh(III) gave an average error of 0.04 mg and a maximum error of 0.66%. The standard deviation was 0.0029.

Procedure for Determination of Rhodium:

Dilute the sample solution containing 10-30 mg of Rh(III) to about 100-125 ml with water. To this add 25 ml of a 1% ethanolic solution of thiophene-2-aldoxime with stirring. Adjust the pH to 10.5-11.0 with dilute NaOH. Digest the precipitate on a water bath for about 30 min. Allow to cool and filter through a preweighed sintered glass crucible